

Quantum-Enabled Secure Simplex FSO Communication with Three-Qubit GHZ State Encoding

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Abstract

Free-space optical (FSO) communication employing intensity modulation exhibits promising potential for achieving elevated data rates. Nonetheless, its susceptibility to security vulnerabilities, stemming from data interception, necessitates proactive measures. To address this, we present a pioneering strategy that integrates quantum encoding and secret sharing, fortifying FSO communication security. Our approach involves utilizing a three-qubit GHZ state to facilitate robust data encryption, ensuring minimal data loss and markedly heightened security. Implementation of our proposed quantum circuit, alongside dedicated transmitting and receiving boards, constitutes the foundational structure for establishing a secure FSO simplex communication setup. This research constitutes a noteworthy stride in secure optical communication, harnessing quantum technologies to safeguard sensitive data. The ramifications of our work extend to potentially improve security paradigms across critical sectors such as military, finance, and data-sensitive domains.

Keywords: FSO, Quantum encoding, Quantum computing, Communication systems

1 Introduction

The free space optics(FSO) communication model transmits data from a transmitter-receiver station via an optical link in a free space medium, achieving high-speed broadband communications [1]. Laser beams are typically employed for this task, although alternative sources such as light-emitting diodes (LEDs) or IR-emitting diodes (IREDS) can achieve the same outcome. Security forms to be of significant concern, and systems employing quantum cryptography provide better security for data transmission through the systems [2]. In the corresponding literature, a simplex FSO communication module is built with a transmitter and receiver section and where the data are encoded by the virtues of QSS (quantum share state) and amplitude encoding and link established using a 650 nm LED. For the corresponding literature, the

Fig. 1: Generic block diagram for the corresponding FSO hardware architecture developed

circuit is built by keeping the basic block diagram shown in Fig 1. The input to the circuit comes from the quantum encoded bits of an electrical signal which in turn goes through intensity modulation for the transmitter, which converts the input electrical signal to an optical signal for the receiving photodiode to receive it. The receiver board converts the optical input signal to an electrical signal, which is further demodulated to be sent to the quantum decoder to retrieve the corresponding transmitted data. This increases the communication module's reliability by using the ideologies of classical secret sharing to quantum secret sharing by using three-qubit GHZ state [3][4]. The transmitter comprises two fundamental constituents: the interface circuit and the source driver circuit. The device's primary purpose is to convert the input signal into an optical signal suitable for transmission. The drive circuit of the transmitter modulates the electrical signal to generate an optical signal by manipulating the current flow in the light source. The principal function of the transmitter is to accurately discharge the aimed optical pulses into the atmosphere. Optical light sources can be classified into two distinct categories: light-emitting diodes (LEDs) and laser diodes (LDs) [5]. The information signal modulates the field of the optical source. The modulated optical field propagates through an unobstructed path until it reaches the receiver. Upon reception, the transmitted data are subjected to inverse operations, wherein the photodetector converts the optical signal into an electrical form, as illustrated in the

figure 1. To explicate, the luminous energy is collected by optical elements such as lenses or mirrors and subsequently detected by a receiver located at the far end of the communication pathway. The received signal is converted back into electrical impulse and transmitted via fiber cable which is connected to the network. Bidirectional data transport in full duplex mode is possible in the reverse direction. Evidently, any task attainable through fiber can also be achieved through free space optics (FSO) [6].

2 Method

2.1 Quantum Secret Sharing (QSS)

Free space optic (FSO) communication comes with one of the major issues modern-day communication faces: security. As stated, the security of FSO systems in the physical layer is compromised if an unknown third party at the transmitter station side can subtract small power from the laser beam. This method easily allows obtaining and decrypting the transmitted data, compromising its security. [7]. Using an encrypted channel over which data are transmitted is much more reliable as with the encryption key, the decryption of the data becomes manageable and easy to proceed. A quantum encoder circuit provides a reliable and secured transmission. A simple three qubit entangled Greenberger-Horne-Zeilinger (GHZ) system is used $\psi_{GHZ} = \frac{|000\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ for encoding operations [3] [8]. The net quantum state of the system results in the arithmetic sums of the complex coefficient of the probabilistic existence in a particular quantum state.

According to the methods mentioned in the simple amplitude encoding scheme where, $\log(n)$ qubits are needed for the representation of data with the simple idea of [9] -

$$X \mapsto \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i |i\rangle \quad (1)$$

Using simple virtue, a custom encoder was developed for the particular encoding operation where a three-qubit GHZ state where the circuit encodes two symbols 0 and 1 into the amplitudes of the qubits. As shown in Fig 2, the implemented circuit q_0 corresponds to state 0 of state one and is encoded in qubits q_1 and q_2 . The corresponding circuit was developed in IBM Quantum Composer and run on *ibmq_mabila*, one of the IBM quantum canary processors [10].

The symbol 0 is encoded into qubit 0 with an amplitude of $\sqrt{0.28}$. This is achieved by applying a Hadamard gate (H), a rotation around the Z-axis (Rz) gate with a rotation angle of 0.68π , and another Hadamard gate to qubit 0. The first Hadamard gate converts the computational basis to a superposition state as [9]-

$$H|0\rangle = |+\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (2)$$

The transformed superposition state is then passed through an Rz gate that provides a rotation of $\exp(-i\frac{\theta}{2}\alpha)$; hence, the action of the $Rz(\alpha)$ gate on $|\psi\rangle$ forward the

Fig. 2: Circuit diagram of the custom quantum encoder for the operation where q_0 is encoded with state 0 and q_1 and q_2 are encoded with state 1.

angle and rotates the state about the z-axis of the bloch sphere through angle α [11]. Providing the equation of the quantum state transmitted to be -

$$R_z(\alpha)|\psi\rangle = \frac{\cos 0.68 \frac{\pi}{2} |0\rangle + e^{i0.68\pi} \sin 0.68 \frac{\pi}{2} |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (3)$$

passing through another Hadamard gate provides a net result of changing the superposition state back to a computational basis and giving the final quantum state equation for the first qubit q_0 to be -

$$|\psi\rangle = \sqrt{0.28}|0\rangle + \sqrt{0.72}|1\rangle \quad (4)$$

Therefore, after applying the encoding operations, the symbol 0 is encoded into qubit 0 with an amplitude of $\sqrt{0.28}$. In this case, the remaining amplitude $\sqrt{0.72}$ corresponds to the symbol 1, encoded into qubit 0. Similarly, when we look after qubits 1 and 2, the superposition state equation for the same after passing through R_z gate is equation 5, while the final state of operation after the Hadamard gate is equation 6-

$$R_z(\alpha)|\psi\rangle = \frac{\cos 0.48 \frac{\pi}{2} |0\rangle + e^{i0.48\pi} \sin 0.48 \frac{\pi}{2} |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (5)$$

$$|\psi\rangle = 0.8|0\rangle + \sqrt{0.36}|1\rangle \quad (6)$$

Therefore, after applying the encoding operations, the symbol one is encoded into qubits 1 and 2 with an amplitude of $\sqrt{0.36}$. In this case, the remaining amplitude 0.8 corresponds to the symbol 0, encoded into qubit 1. They give an encoded system where the entire transmitted data are encoded to symbols 0 and 1 with $\sqrt{0.28}$ and $\sqrt{0.36}$ amplitudes, respectively. The server of *ibmq_maniila* was used, where 1024 shots were fired to determine the probabilistic values of each quantum state.

The corresponding GHZ state for the encoded circuit where 3 qubit entanglement is used produces a net of 8 states each with a complex coefficient with the probabilistic

(a) Fig 3a demonstrates the phase to angle for the corresponding quantum state and the corresponding location on the Q-Sphere

(b) Figure 3b demonstrates the state vector representation for the same corresponding states to the amplitude encoded each individual state.

occurrence of each element in each state as shown in Table 1 and the corresponding phase angles are shown in Fig.3a and the state vector representation can be observed in Fig.3b.

According to Table 1, the transmitted qubits are in an entangled state and transmitted with each output state as a complex coefficient. The corresponding circuit is run, and the outputs for the transmitted shots can be observed by showing the number of shots in the corresponding state after transmission and the stimulated probability of each of the states observed.

The corresponding table represents the composer's output with the number of shots fired, generating the probability of existence in each state with the mathematically calculated probability with each corresponding output state amplitude for the same state. The provided quantum circuit acts as an encoder with a satisfactory encoding operation. The net variations between the calculated and transported values are due to quantum noise and errors.

Analysis for the corresponding output states			
Quantum states	Mathematically Calculated Probabilities	Output States	Frequency of shots received
$ 000\rangle$	19.72656%	$-0.3 - 0.319j$	210
$ 001\rangle$	7.22656%	$0.176 - 0.165j$	81
$ 010\rangle$	17.96875%	$-0.3 + 0.319j$	191
$ 011\rangle$	5.76172%	$-0.176 - 0.165j$	53
$ 100\rangle$	18.75%	$0.3 + 0.319j$	182
$ 101\rangle$	6.54297%	$-0.176 + 0.165j$	56
$ 110\rangle$	17.96875%	$-0.3 + 0.319j$	201
$ 111\rangle$	6.05469%	$-0.176 - 0.165j$	50

Table 1: Mathematical and stimulated analysis is performed on the quantum circuit and the transported shots to the corresponding quantum states were measured and observed using the IBM Quantum Composer. The corresponding values correspond to the mathematical states of the individual quantum states from $|000\rangle$ to $|111\rangle$.

2.2 Hardware schematic

The simplex communication hardware embedded in the system can transmit and receive Ethernet data utilizing a dedicated transmitter and receiver board [12]. It is imperative to devise distinct circuits for each of the boards. The system communicates with the data generators using RJ45 female ports on the printed circuit board (PCB). A feasible approach to establish a connection with the computer involves the utilization of a male-to-male USB to RJ45 adapter. The initial input is introduced to the transmitter circuit via the +Tx and -Tx pins of the Ethernet RJ45 port, located at pins 3 and 6, respectively. An operational amplifier provides a bias for the laser diode to ensure optimal operation. Inductors and capacitors are incorporated to isolate the laser diode from the bias stage and the AC input [13].

The transmitter circuit developed in Fig 4 employs intensity modulation, whereby the optical signal intensity is modulated in response to the input AC Ethernet signal, resulting in changes in the intensity of the optical signal relative to a specific DC operating current.

The receiver aims to detect the optical signal generated by its corresponding transmitter board, convert it into an electrical signal, and transmit it via the receive (RX) cable pair of the connected ethernet cable. Fig. 5, containing the receiver schematic, shows the first phase. A trans-impedance amplifier converts the photocurrent of a reverse-biased photo-diode (SFH203P) [15] into a power signal with a gain of 1 kOhm. After this stage, the signal maintains a relatively weak strength and is vulnerable to potential interference. The utilization of a comparator (MAX913) is implemented to enhance transmission via the ethernet cable [16].

The apparatus is furnished with both inverted and noninverted outputs, thereby enabling the functioning of a differential cable pair. Unfortunately, the device in question does not meet the criteria for high output current, specifically 5 volts into 100 ohms differential. As a result, it is necessary to utilize an auxiliary, dual operational amplifier, such as MAX4392, as a buffer [17]. The selection of a suitable laser source for free space optics (FSO) applications depends on various factors. The relationship between the transmission wavelength and an atmospheric window is significant.

Fig. 4: Transmitter schematic: RJ45 positioned on the left of the schematic used for data transmission with exposed pin 3 and 6 to circuit for transmitting the data to the system while the operational amplifier providing a bias is placed on the right with it's corresponding components used. [14]

The atmospheric windows that are considered optimal are found within the shorter IR wavelength range, particularly at approximately 850 nm and 1550 nm. In the extended infrared spectral range, specific intervals of wavelengths are detectable, such as the 3-5 micrometer range [18]. The availability of suitable light sources in these expanded wavelength ranges is significantly limited. A laser diode operating within the visible range and emitting light at a wavelength of 650 nm is currently in use. The characteristics of the selected laser diode can be viewed in Fig 6.

Fig. 6: Laser diode power vs forward current [19]

The photodiode selection process was guided by several specifications, including but not limited to the wavelength of maximum sensitivity, which is crucial for detecting incoming laser light, the wavelength of operation, which pertains to visible light wavelengths, quantum efficiency, and responsivity. The rationale behind selecting PIN photodiodes was based on their cost-effectiveness and widespread availability. The implementation of avalanche photodiodes (APDs) has demonstrated a performance improvement and has enabled a more convenient comparison with PIN photodiodes [20]. The SFH203P photodiode was employed in the present investigation, displaying a wavelength response spectrum of approximately 400nm to 1100nm [15], situated within the visible range. The maximum response of the system occurs at a wavelength of 850 nm, exhibiting a responsivity of 0.62 A/W and a current of $80\mu A$. The laser diode's light detection sensitivity is acceptable when operating at a wavelength of 650 nm, reaching approximately 75 percent of its maximum sensitivity.

3 Results and Discussion

OptiSystem is a software application utilized in the design and simulation of optical communication systems [21]. The software enables users to replicate a diverse array of optical components and systems, encompassing systems for communication via free-space optical channels. A rudimentary LED-centric setup was evaluated to emulate a free-space optical communication system within the framework of the OptiSystem which is demonstrated in Fig 7.

Fig. 7: System simulation in Optisystem. The output power was compared to the input power at the terminals of the NRZ generator. A loss of 2dm was observed under ideal circumstances

An LED is being utilized as the light source for simulation purposes, and random bits encoded with an NRZ pulse generator are being delivered to it. Subsequently, we proceeded to simulate a channel within an unobstructed environment. At the onset of the channel, a photodiode and a transimpedance amplifier (TIA) are employed. Subsequently, an optical power meter is employed to assess the magnitude of the output power. In Fig 8, a square wave with a frequency of 10 MHz is applied as input to

Fig. 8: Transmitter simulation, The figure depicts the outcome of the simulation conducted on the transmitter circuit using TINA software. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the unavailability of a laser diode model in both TINA and Multisim, a simple resistance was simulated to fulfill this function.

VG1 in the transmitter circuit provided. The circuit under consideration incorporates a laser diode, specifically resistor R1, which necessitates a bias current. To this end, we have provided it with a current of 19 mA. The output waveform of this laser diode is a square wave with a frequency of 10 MHz. This waveform can be visualized across the simulated R1 by manipulating the variable resistor linked to the operational amplifier's non-inverting terminal. Enclosed herewith are the outcomes. The waveform of AM 1, as observed from the transmitter, exhibits a fluctuating direct current of approximately 19 milliamperes. The VG1 and VG2 waveforms simulate Ethernet waveforms, while Vm represents the voltage across R1. The receiver stimulation in Fig 9 depicts a

Fig. 9: Total Receiver Simulation, The figure depicts the outcome of the simulation conducted on the receiver circuit using TINA software.

simulated receiver trans-impedance amplifier using TINA software. A 10 MHz square wave current source was employed to validate the correct functioning of the TIA. The findings of the simulations indicate that the Transimpedance Amplifier (TIA) generates square waveforms with a gain of 1k at frequencies associated with square waves. The input current of IG1 is recorded at a frequency of 10 MHz, while the output voltage waveform, Vm1, is also measured at the same frequency. Subsequently, the wave is directed toward an inverter circuit, specifically an inverted Schmitt trigger, to guarantee compatibility with RJ 45. The attached circuit shows that the input is a current square wave at 10 MHz (in place of the photodiode), and the output is the exact inversion of that voltage wave with increased amplitude to 5 V and 0 V for compatibility with an RJ 45 plug.

The frequency response of the trans-impedance amplifier (TIA) was analyzed on the receiving end, and the output obtained is shown in Fig 10, revealing a 3 dB bandwidth of approximately 100 MHz. Subsequently, the feedback resistance was increased, resulting in a gain increase from 60 dB to 80 dB when raised to 8k. The allocated frequency range was reduced to approximately 12 megahertz. The gain selection is contingent upon the current produced by the photodiode, as a higher gain is necessary when the current is lower. A direct relationship exists between the gain and bandwidth of the circuit, whereby an increase in gain results in a decrease in bandwidth.

Fig. 10: Receiver frequency response, A gain of 1k ohm was utilized in our scenario to achieve an ideal bandwidth of 12 Mhz

Fig. 11: Transmitter Frequency Response exhibiting an optimal 3 decibel bandwidth of approximately 80 megahertz.

Hardware testing and assembly were performed on the transmitter and receiver PCB. The connection was established where the encrypted data are transmitted via the Ethernet RJ45 port to the transmitter board, the electrical signal is converted to an optical signal and transmitted through a laser diode of 650 nm wavelength, and the receiver board is situated with its photodiode at a considerable distance when the laser diode illuminates the photodiode at the receiver the connection is completed. The signal is passed to the trans-impedance amplifier, the buffer circuit, and the comparator. The output is measured through the +Rx and -Rx pins of the RJ45 connector using a DSO. The final unified output for the same is obtained; in Fig 12, the left panel demonstrates the signal input power to the circuit, and the output in Fig 12, the right panel demonstrates the corresponding obtained output-

The encrypted data are transmitted successfully via the simplex communication transmitter and receiver boards.

Fig. 12: Left: The input provided to the transmitter board with 2.088 MHz frequency calibrated square wave signal, Right: The output from the receiver board for the corresponding input retrieving the square wave with 2.0881 MHz measured on DSO.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the combination of free space optic (FSO) communication, intensity modulation, and quantum technologies holds great promise for achieving high-speed data rates while addressing security concerns. We have proposed a novel approach to secure FSO communication by integrating quantum encoding and secret-sharing techniques. Our solution utilizes a three-qubit GHZ state for robust data encryption, enhancing security and minimizing data loss. The developed quantum circuit and dedicated transmitting and receiving boards provide the foundation for our secure FSO simplex communication system. This research significantly contributes to secure optical communication, as it leverages quantum principles to protect sensitive data and prevent unauthorized interception. The potential impact of this work extends to various domains, including military applications, financial institutions, and other data-sensitive sectors. By revolutionizing security measures in these areas, our research paves the way for improved protection and confidentiality of critical information. Future advancements in quantum-enabled secure FSO communication can shape the landscape of secure data transmission and drive progress in secure communication technologies.

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5 Declarations

Ethical Approval. No testing on humans or animals was performed, and no humans or animals were harmed during the process of the research

Competing interests. Not Applicable

Data Access. Yes the consent for publicly available data is in consent with the authors

Authors' contributions. All authors have contributed equally. All authors have reviewed the manuscript,

- YG: Worked on hardware implementation of the FSO of designing and integrating the transmitter
- SH: Worked on QSS part of designing implementing and sharing the input data to the transmitter
- HK: Worked on Hardware Implementation of the FSO of designing and integrating the Receiver
- MA: Worked on writing the paper

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Consent to participate. All participants have consent

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